

Position Paper

Input to the Consultancy Request of the European Commission on its Initiative „Towards European Open Digital Ecosystems“

Interest Group 'Digital Tools and their Development, including Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning' within the Alliance Focus 'Digitality in Science' of the Alliance of Science Organisations in Germany

Summary of Comments

We, the Interest Group 'Digital Tools and their Development, including Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning' within the Alliance Focus 'Digitality in Science', encourage the EU commission to foster the attractiveness of the open source market for providers in the EU with this envisioned initiative. The EU open source sector should now be considered in terms of its paramount importance for the digital security and digital sovereignty of EU and its Member States. Emphasis should be laid on the political necessity and political will to significantly reduce dependence on international technology giants. European money spent within the EU on open source software adds to a more stable internal European economy.

Academic and research institutions are experienced in designing and implementing open source solutions. Open source software in research is highly accepted to support reproducibility of scientific findings and trustworthiness of research. Additionally, open source can enhance knowledge and technology transfer from academic research into commercial applications. The adoption of open source software corresponds to open science approaches, mitigates the risk of vendor lock-in and fosters competition in the development of optimal solutions for end-users, thereby benefiting society. Support for existing open source providers and networks and for research-related open source software offerings for European higher education systems would be of great benefit.

Another important context is open source for generative AI models and tools through the provision and devel-

opment of open source AI. This is especially important for open training data, open model weights, and open AI algorithms.

Universities and research institutions are exposed to an increased risk of cyber attacks, often with long-term consequences in reputation and financial expenses. The increased use of open source software can help to mitigate hazards and reduces the risk of significant internal organisational and economic damage to scientific organisations. A consistent combination of open source code and cybersecurity through increased use of open source-based, trustworthy solutions in software or hardware, such as RISC-V microcontrollers, could be effective. Open source trust anchors have to be promoted and used particularly in security-critical areas. Examples are technology-neutral 5G and 6G test environments (i.e., the Open RAN concept).

It is also desirable to strive for the implementation of rules for publicly funded institutions and projects requiring them to use a certain amount of open source software, if possible.

Strengthening these efforts by means of additional funding opportunities for open source software projects and their use in publicly funded projects and institutions would be beneficial for academia and society. It enhances digital sovereignty and in addition reduces the potential for state-guided coercion through the manipulation of software or disturbance of services.

Detailed Comments to the Guiding Questions:

1. What are the strengths and weaknesses of the EU open-source sector? What are the main barriers that hamper (i) adoption and maintenance of high-quality and secure open source; and (ii) sustainable contributions to open-source communities?

The EU open source sector has so far been a niche market and should now be fundamentally reassessed

in terms of its critical importance to the digital autonomy and security of the EU and its Member States. The emphasis on strengthening the competitiveness of the open source sector in the draft text is understandable, but the argument should focus primarily on the absolute political and economical necessity of significantly reducing dependence on international technology giants. This necessity also includes support for open source-based large language models in order to reduce dependence on international providers of proprietary solutions in this area as well.

One barrier to the use of open source software is that, like proprietary software, it incurs (follow-up) costs when it is introduced and/or when support is required during ongoing operation. Such costs are typically not covered by project funding. Public funding for these follow-up costs would significantly increase the willingness to use open source systems in academic and research environments.

2. What is the added value of open source for the public and private sectors? Please provide concrete examples, including the factors (such as cost, risk, lock-in, security, innovation, among others) that are most important to assess the added value.

At a time when universities and research institutions are already exposed to an increased risk of cyber attacks, often with long-term and costly consequences, the increased use of open source software in all core areas of higher education and non-university research institutions helps them to mitigate risks and reduces the risk of significant internal organisational and economic damage. However, if open source software does indeed achieve a similarly widespread use within the EU in the future as proprietary software currently enjoys, it cannot be ruled out that these systems could also become more frequent targets of cyber attacks in the medium term. At present, however, this is not foreseeable. Open source software also avoids the currently excessive costs for licences for day-to-day standard tasks that are currently performed using costly proprietary software.

In addition, the use open source as part of the research process enables researchers to tailor software solutions to their specific needs, supports reproducibility and reuse of scientific findings, and enhances transparency and trustworthiness of the research system as a whole. Open source software regularly comes along with the use of open and documented file formats that are less vulnerable to cyber attacks, and additionally it can enhance knowledge and technology transfer from academic research into commercial applications. Open source software also provides valuable learning opportunities for university students, enabling them to engage with real-life, production-level codebases and potentially contribute to real-world projects.

The adoption of open source software mitigates the risk

of vendor lock-in and fosters competition in the development of optimal and affordable solutions for end-users.

Securing talent in EU by providing favourable conditions to engage with or even work regularly from open source software in research, teaching and learning and administration at universities and non-university research institutions leads to a long-term sustainable software future. European money spent within the EU on open source software also adds to a more stable internal economy.

3. What concrete measures and actions may be taken at EU level to support the development and growth of the EU open source sector and contribute to the EU's technological sovereignty and cybersecurity agenda?

A bold public stance by the European Commission in favour of open source infrastructures would be helpful. Support for existing open source providers and networks and for research-related open software offerings for European higher education systems would be of great benefit: Additional funding for open source software projects, their general deployment, their use in publicly funded projects and institutions and their long-term maintenance is required. In cases where suitable open source alternatives are available, it is also desirable to strive for the implementation of rules for publicly funded institutions and projects requiring them to use them.

In addition, the EU Commission may enable or provide funding schemes for collaboration between the public and private sectors. The open source world usually misses the commercial management layer, but collaborative processes like community management, requirements engineering or integration require support.

4. What technology areas should be prioritised and why?

Open source productivity software and research software should both be prioritised. A consistent combination of open source code and cybersecurity through increased use of open source-based, trustworthy solutions in software or hardware, such as RISC-V

microcontrollers, could be effective. Open source trust anchors have to be promoted and used particularly in security-critical areas. To give an example, it seems advisable to establish and expand technology-neutral 5G and 6G test environments to accelerate implementation and support application development. In particular, the Open RAN concept should be supported. Additionally, open source for generative AI models and tools through the provision and development of open source AI is required. The demand for innovation-driven open source AI components is on the rise, such as open training data, open model weights, and open AI algorithms. The EU commission should strive for making participation in the open source market more attractive for local providers and securing European values and design options.

5. In what sectors could an increased use of open source lead to increased competitiveness and cyber resilience?

In the research and education system, the prioritised use of open source software would help to significantly reduce the excessive number of extremely costly cyber attacks. These attacks most frequently affect educational institutions that primarily use the systems of technology giants. Furthermore, prioritising open source solutions aligns with open science approaches, enhances digital sovereignty and reduces the potential for state-guided coercion through the manipulation of software or disturbance of services. An additional benefit of open source software is often the usage of open data formats, which makes computing interoperable and thus creates the potential for an ecosystem of exchangeable components.

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